

1 **Mixed Bayesian Network for reliability assessment of RC structures subject** 2 **to environmental actions**

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7 **Abstract:** Under environmental action, reinforced concrete (RC) structures might suffer from
8 reinforcement corrosion caused by the surrounding environment, dramatically reducing
9 structural reliability and threatening social development. However, most of the existing
10 reliability assessment methods for RC structures only focused on the structural performance at
11 the design stage given the original unchanged environment, ignoring the effects of realistic
12 exposure conditions and inspection results on reliability evaluation. Thus, this paper develops
13 a general reliability assessment framework based on a Mixed Bayesian network (MBN),
14 incorporating three modules, i.e., durability assessment, load-bearing capacity analysis, and
15 time-dependent reliability analysis. In MBN, separate sub-BNs are built based on different
16 modules and connected by pinch point variables where probabilistic information is transmitted
17 via soft evidence. Besides, this framework considers time-dependent environmental parameters
18 and two-dimensional chloride transport and their effects on reliability. Meanwhile, adjustment
19 coefficients are applied to improve the results of the analytical mechanical model with respect
20 to different limit states through the finite element model (FEM). The proposed MBN framework
21 is illustrated for a corroded RC beam under a marine atmospheric environment to investigate
22 the effects of environmental modeling, chloride transport patterns, and concrete crack
23 inspection on reliability assessment. The results indicate that early inspection of high-level
24 cracks may significantly increase the failure probability by about 500%. Besides, failure
25 probability might be reduced by about 95%, ignoring the time-variant environment and two-
26 dimensional chloride transport.

27 **Keywords:** Bayesian Network; Reliability Assessment; Reinforced Concrete; Environmental
28 Actions; Reinforcement Corrosion

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29 **1. Introduction**

30 During the service life of reinforced concrete (RC) structures, their mechanical performances
31 deteriorate over time due to long-term environmental impacts (e.g., chloride ingress and
32 concrete carbonation etc.) [1–3]. According to ASCE 2021 report card for America's
33 infrastructure [4], there are 46,154 bridges representing 7.5% of the overall bridges in the USA,
34 with structural deficiencies. The costs for overcoming the detrimental impacts of structural
35 deficiencies are enormous and intractable. In 2022, a study by the financial accountability office
36 of Ontario estimated that \$10.1 billion should be annually spent to keep a safe state in the
37 existing local portfolio of public buildings and facilities [5]. Therefore, this deterioration of
38 structural performance could produce severe direct and indirect social impacts – e.g., delays,
39 unavailability of structure assets, etc.

40 Various studies indicated that RC structural performance is mainly caused by chloride or
41 carbonation-induced reinforcement corrosion [3,6]. Consequently, many efforts have been
42 made to assess the reliability of corroded RC structures over time. In 1997, Frangopol *et al.* [7]
43 proposed a reliability assessment method for RC girders subject to chloride ingress and
44 implemented reliability-based life-cycle cost evaluation. Furthermore, considering the pitting
45 corrosion and its spatial effects on RC structures, Stewart and his collaborators [8–11]
46 conducted a series of research relating to Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) based reliability
47 analysis. Similarly, Val [12] investigated the time-dependent reliability of corroded RC beams
48 subject to different failure modes, including flexural and shear failure. Guo *et al.* [13] developed
49 a two-step translation method to perform the time-dependent reliability analysis for corroded
50 RC structures efficiently. However, these studies focused on a fixed environment, while
51 realistic environmental conditions combine time dependency, nonlinearity, and uncertainty.
52 Therefore, Bastidas-Arteaga *et al.* [14] proposed a reliability assessment method for RC

53 structures with respect to the effects of carbon emissions-induced climate change on structural
54 performance. In addition, the existing studies associated with the reliability assessment of RC
55 structures usually applied analytical models and lacked experimental validation [15]. Thus,
56 Zhang *et al.* [16] used Finite Element Modeling (FEM) and X-ray photographs integrated with
57 experimental validation and MCS to achieve the reliability analysis of corroded RC beams. Guo
58 *et al.* [17] also employed experimental validation, FEM, and polynomial chaos expansions to
59 develop a general framework of global sensitivity and probabilistic analysis for failure analysis
60 of corroded RC structures. However, these studies focused on their reliability assessment at the
61 design stage, which ignores actual exposure conditions and inspection results, and might
62 misestimate the capacity and reliability of RC structures. Therefore, it is still necessary to
63 consider the above-mentioned aspects to improve the reliability assessment/updating of RC
64 structures.

65 Bayesian methods have been commonly utilized to perform probabilistic inference by
66 updating the data collected from monitoring systems or in-situ inspections [18]. Since many
67 parameters (environmental, material, etc.) are involved in practical engineering systems, it
68 might be challenging to use traditional Bayesian methods for parameter updating and inference.
69 To this end, a graphical model called Bayesian Network (BN) has been widely applied to update
70 the reliability assessment of RC structures through probabilistic inspection data [19,20]. For
71 instance, considering carbonation-induced reinforcement corrosion, Tesfamariam and Martín-
72 Pérez [21] built a BN model to investigate the effects of exposure conditions on the carbonation
73 rate and the corrosion probability. Deby *et al.* [22,23] applied BN to implement reliability
74 analysis for RC structures subject to chloride ingress. Tran *et al.* [24–26] conducted a series of
75 studies to identify the uncertainties of parameters and corrosion initiation probability for
76 deteriorating RC structures under chloride ingress. However, those studies usually adopted

77 static Bayesian Networks (SBN), which did not consider the time-dependency of some
78 parameters involved in the problem – e.g., concrete aging, surface chloride concentration,
79 loading, etc. Therefore, to handle BN updating and inferences under multiple time slices,
80 Dynamic Bayesian Network (DBN) has been proposed [27,28]. For instance, Guo and Dong [2]
81 developed a general DBN framework for the durability assessment of RC structures with
82 respect to the marine atmospheric environment. Considering the uncertainties in climate change
83 and chloride transport, such a framework could investigate the effects of inspected concrete
84 cracks on the durability of RC structures. However, such a DBN framework only concerns the
85 durability assessment of RC structures rather than their mechanical properties. Therefore, the
86 study cannot be directly applied to the time-dependent reliability assessment of RC structures
87 under environmental actions when focusing on ultimate limit states.

88 In order to perform a BN-based life-cycle reliability analysis for corroded RC structures,
89 it is imperative to consider the effects of environmental-induced reinforcement corrosion on the
90 performance of RC structures. For example, Ma *et al.* [29] established a BN integrating with
91 in-situ loading tests to predict the performance deterioration and structural response of existing
92 corroded RC bridges. However, due to the absence of DBN, this study might be inappropriate
93 for the time-dependent reliability analysis of RC structures. Thus, Hackl and Kohler [30]
94 proposed a DBN framework for the reliability assessment of corroded RC structures subject to
95 chloride transport by integrating parameters associated with the deterioration process. Although
96 this study considers time dependencies using DBN, many issues still need to be addressed. For
97 instance, such an existing DBN framework did not consider climate change and applied a
98 simplified one-dimensional Fick's law for chloride transport prediction, which might lead to
99 errors on the durability performance and reliability assessments under realistic exposure
100 conditions and two-dimensional chloride ingress (RC beams and columns) [1,31,32]. In

101 addition, the existing DBN framework still adopted analytical mechanical models and ignored
102 the corrosion-induced spatial effects, which might misestimate the mechanical performance and
103 reliability level of RC structures. These issues could be solved by considering comprehensive
104 deterioration models such as those in [14,17,33]. However, the computational cost for the BN
105 modeling and inference would grow exponentially for this type of model that requires several
106 input parameters [19,20]. Therefore, there is still a need to propose a novel BN framework for
107 RC structural reliability assessment/updating, doing a trade-off between model complexity and
108 efficiency.

109 This study proposes a comprehensive BN framework for the life-cycle reliability
110 assessment of RC structures under the marine atmospheric environment. The framework
111 incorporates several physical models for the durability and reliability assessment/updating of
112 RC structures, including a two-dimensional chloride transport model and analytical and finite
113 element methods for RC structural performance analysis (Section 3). In order to reduce the
114 difficulty in BN modeling involving many parameters, this paper establishes a new Mixed
115 Bayesian Network (MBN). The basic idea of MBN is to build sub-BNs in terms of various
116 physical and mathematical models and then connect all sub-BNs via pinch-point variables to
117 realize reliability analysis under various limit states (Section 4). Finally, the proposed MBN
118 framework is illustrated with a time-dependent reliability analysis of RC beams placed in a
119 marine atmospheric environment. In this case study, we examine the effects of environmental
120 models, patterns of chloride transport, and inspection results on reliability assessment/updating.

121 **2. Principal concepts of the proposed framework**

122 As illustrated in Fig.1, the proposed framework for the reliability assessment of RC structures
123 consists of three main stages: durability, mechanical, and reliability assessment. In the first stage
124 of durability assessment, the boundary conditions of the structure (external temperature, relative

125 humidity, and chloride concentration) are obtained via environmental modeling. A chloride
126 transport model is used to determine the corrosion initiation time. When corrosion initiates, the
127 corrosion rate i_{corr} and the radius reduction of reinforcement Δr could be evaluated. The
128 numerical model for this first stage has been developed in a previous study [2]. The main results
129 of stage 1 (i_{corr} and Δr) are transferred to the next stage (mechanical evaluation) to assess
130 flexural and shear capacity (P_{Mu} and P_{Vu}) and to carry out FEM analysis. In the last stage,
131 reliability assessment and failure mode analysis are performed in terms of the results of the
132 mechanical assessment in the second stage. The mechanical evaluation and reliability
133 computation models are detailed in Section 3. Direct implementation of such a framework
134 through BN is computationally challenging since it introduces many parameters associated with
135 various models. This study proposes an MBN to address this challenge of updating information
136 and probabilistic inference without developing a large and complex BN. MBN is built and
137 updated at each stage by integrating different models and analysis methods, and the pinch point
138 variables (i_{corr} , Δr , P_{Mu} , and P_{Vu}) serve as a bridge between various sub-BNs. The MBN method
139 is introduced in Section 4.

140 **3. Performance assessment models of RC structures**

141 **3.1. Durability assessment of RC structures**

142 In this section, the basic models employed in the durability assessment, including
143 environmental modeling, chloride transport prediction, and corrosion degree and concrete crack
144 evaluations, are briefly reviewed from previous studies [2,34].

145 **3.1.1. Environmental modeling and chloride ingress**

146 Realistic modeling of environmental parameters, e.g., temperature, relative humidity (RH), and
147 chloride deposition, is essential for the durability assessment of RC structures. Thus, an

148 environmental model is adopted to consider: the characteristic value of exposure conditions ec ,
 149 the seasonal $f_{sea}(t)$ and daily variations $f_{dai}(t)$, an increasing tendency f_{inc} , and a white noise ξ ,
 150 as presented in Eqs.(1)-(4) [1,35]. Given the parameters in Eqs.(1)-(4) and ec , temperature,
 151 relative humidity (RH), and chloride deposition at any time instant could be calculated.

$$152 \quad f(ec, t) = f_{sea}(t) + f_{dai}(t) + f_{inc}(ec, t) + \xi \quad (1)$$

$$153 \quad f_{sea}(t) = a_1 \cdot \sin[w_1(t - t_{ref})/365 + b_1] + a_2 \cdot \sin[2w_1(t - t_{ref})/365 + b_2] + a_0 \quad (2)$$

$$154 \quad f_{dai}(t) = a_{01} - a_{11} \cos(w_{11}t) + b_{11} \sin(w_{11}t) - a_{21} \cos(2w_{11}t) - b_{21} \sin(2w_{11}t) \quad (3)$$

$$155 \quad f_{inc}(ec, t) = (5.04 \times 10^{-3} ec^2 - 3.57 \times 10^{-2} ec + 6.49 \times 10^{-2}) \cdot [(t - t_{ref})/365]^{0.359ec + 0.333} \quad (4)$$

156 where t and t_{ref} are current and reference time (day); a_0 is the baseline average mean annual
 157 value; a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, w_1 , and w_2 are the parameters of $f_{sea}(t)$; and $a_{01}, a_{11}, a_{21}, b_{11}, b_{21}$ and w_{11} are
 158 the parameters of $f_{dai}(t)$. In section 5, an example of this model is presented. Given the boundary
 159 conditions provided by Eqs.(1)-(4), the chloride ingress process into concrete could be
 160 simulated by the following three steps [1]:

161 (1) Solve the heat transfer equation, i.e., Eq. (5) [36]

$$162 \quad \rho_c \cdot c_q \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \lambda \nabla T = \lambda \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (5)$$

163 where T is the current temperature (K); x and y are the horizontal and vertical coordinates (m)
 164 of cross-sections; ρ_c, c_q , and λ are denoted as concrete density, heat capacity, and thermal
 165 conductivity, respectively.

166 (2) Solve the moisture diffusion equation, i.e., Eq. (6) [31];

$$167 \quad \frac{\partial w_e}{\partial h_{RH}} \frac{\partial h_{RH}}{\partial t} = D_h \left(\frac{\partial h_{RH}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial h_{RH}}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

168 where h_{RH} is the relative humidity (RH) inside the concrete, and D_h is the coefficient of humidity
 169 diffusion (m^2/s) related to T, t , and RH [37].

170 (3) Solve the chloride transport equation, i.e., Eq. (7) [31].

171
$$\frac{\partial C_{fc}}{\partial t} = D_c^* \left(\frac{\partial^2 C_{fc}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C_{fc}}{\partial y^2} \right) + D_h^* \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(C_{fc} \frac{\partial h_{RH}}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(C_{fc} \frac{\partial h_{RH}}{\partial y} \right) \right) \quad (7)$$

172 where C_{fc} is free chloride content (kg/m^3 of pore solution); and D_c^* and D_h^* are the apparent
 173 diffusion coefficients of chlorides and moisture (m^2/s), respectively. The alternating-direction
 174 implicit-based finite difference method is employed to solve Eqs. (5)-(7) [38] due to its high
 175 nonlinearity and two-dimensional formulation.

176 3.1.2. Reinforcement corrosion and concrete cracking

177 The simulation of chloride transport in Section 3.1.1 provides the chloride content on the
 178 reinforcement surface c_{bar} . The reinforcement corrosion would start once c_{bar} is beyond critical
 179 value c_{cr} . After corrosion initiation, the corrosion rate of reinforcement is evaluated by Liu's
 180 model [39]:

181
$$\ln[1.08i_{corr}(t)] = 7.89 + 0.7771 \cdot \ln(1.69c_{bar}) - \frac{3006}{T_{con}} - 1.16 \times 10^4 \cdot R_{con} + 2.24t_{corr}^{-0.215} + \mathcal{G} \quad (8)$$

182 where $i_{corr}(t)$ is the corrosion current density ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$); T_{con} and R_{con} (Ohms) are the temperature
 183 and resistance within the concrete; t_{corr} (year) is the time after corrosion initiation; and \mathcal{G} denotes
 184 a white noise following $N(0, 0.3312)$ [35]. According to Faraday's law, the reduction of
 185 reinforcement radius $\Delta r(t)$, the cross-sectional area $\Delta A_s(t)$, and average corrosion degree $\eta_{ave}(t)$
 186 are respectively expressed by Eqs. (9), (10) and (11).

187
$$\Delta r(t) = \int_0^t 0.0116i_{corr}(t) dt \quad (9)$$

188
$$\Delta A_s(t) = \pi d_0^2 - A_{ave}(t) = \pi d_0^2 - \pi [d_0 - 2 \cdot \Delta r(t)]^2 \quad (10)$$

189
$$\eta_{ave}(t) = [1 - A_{ave}(t)] / (\pi d_0^2) \quad (11)$$

190 where d_0 is the initial steel bar diameter; and $A_{ave}(t)$ is the average residual cross-sectional area
 191 of the corroded steel bar. In terms of the loss of cross-sectional area, the corrosion-induced
 192 crack width ω (mm) is evaluated by an empirical model [40]:

193
$$\omega(t) = 0.0575 \cdot [\Delta A_s(t) - \Delta A_{s0}], \Delta A_{s0} = \pi d_0^2 \left\{ 1 - \left[1 - 2/d_0 (7.53 + 9.32c_t/d_0) 10^{-3} \right]^2 \right\} \quad (12)$$

194 where ΔA_{s0} is the reduction of the cross-sectional area once concrete cracks; and c_t (mm) is the
 195 cover thickness of RC structures. Furthermore, considering the influence of corrosion-induced
 196 cracks on the durability performance of RC structures, the diffusion coefficients of chloride
 197 D_c^ω and humidity D_h^ω for cracked concrete are evaluated by Eqs.(13) [41] and (14) [42],
 198 respectively.

199
$$D_c^\omega = f_{\omega 1}(\omega) \cdot D_c^*(t), f_{\omega 1}(\omega) = 31.61\omega^2 + 4.73\omega + 1, \omega \geq 0.1mm \quad (13)$$

200
$$D_h^\omega = f_{\omega 2}(\omega) \cdot D_h^*(t), f_h(\omega) = 1 + k_h \cdot \omega^3 / s_h \quad (14)$$

201 where k_h is an environmental parameter (10^5 mm^{-2} [42]); and s_h is the mean crack which is
 202 assumed to be 250 mm in this study [42].

203 3.2.Mechanical capacity of a corroded RC beam

204 This study investigated the mechanical behavior of a simply supported corroded RC beam with
 205 a rectangular cross-section (Fig.2). The total and effective length, cover thickness, and stirrup
 206 spacing of the beam are l , l_{eff} , c , and s_v , respectively, and the cross-sectional width, total height,
 207 and effective height are denoted as b , h , and h_0 , respectively. Existing studies proved that
 208 chloride attack generally induced non-uniform reinforcement corrosion, which further causes
 209 spatial variability in the mechanical capacities of corroded RC beams. Therefore, failure could
 210 occur in other positions than span mid-point [43,44]. To account for the spatial variability, the
 211 beams are separated into m zones concerning the spatial effects of corrosion non-uniformity on
 212 the mechanical performance of RC beams, as shown in Fig.2. The non-uniform reinforcement
 213 corrosion is quantified by the corrosion non-uniformity factor $R(t)$, i.e., [43]

214
$$R(t) = A_{\text{ave}}(t) / A_{\text{min}}(t) \quad (15)$$

215 where $A_{\text{min}}(t)$ is the minimum cross-sectional area at time t . Existing study shows that factor

216 $R(t)$ follows a Gumbel distribution whose distribution parameters μ and σ could be computed
 217 by Eqs. (16) and (17), respectively [1,43]. For the sake of simplicity, the factor R and the
 218 minimum cross-sectional area of each zone are supposed to be independent of the others [13,43].

$$219 \quad \mu(t) = 3.35 \cdot \eta_{\text{ave}}(t) \exp[-0.236i_{\text{corr}}(t)] + 0.12 \cdot \eta_{\text{ave}}(t) + 1.01 \quad (16)$$

$$220 \quad \sigma(t) = 0.3371\eta_{\text{ave}}(t) + 0.0006 \quad (17)$$

221 3.2.1. Analytical mechanical models of RC beam

222 Based on several assumptions, analytical mechanical models could be applied to yield the time-
 223 dependent mechanical capacities of RC beams in a rapid manner. For instance, supposing RC
 224 beams with planar sections are well-anchored and completely bonded during their service lives,
 225 their flexural capacities $M_{u,k}(t)$ at each zone can be calculated by Eq.(18) [13,43].

$$226 \quad M_{u,k}(t) = F_{y,k}(t) \cdot [h_0 - 0.5 F_{y,k}(t)/(b \cdot f_c)] \quad (18)$$

227 where f_c is the concrete compressive strength (MPa); and $F_{y,k}(t)$ (N) is the capacity of corroded
 228 tension rebars of the k -th zone at time t , which could be expressed by Eq.(19).

$$229 \quad F_{y,k}(t) = f_{y0} \cdot A_k^t(t) \quad (19)$$

230 where f_{y0} is the yield strength of uncorroded tension bars; $A_k^t(t)$ is the equivalent cross-sectional
 231 area of tension bars in the k -th zone. Considering the effects of corrosion on the ductility of
 232 corroded steel bars, $A_k^t(t)$ is computed by Eq.(20).

$$233 \quad A_k^t(t) = \max_{j=1}^{n_t} [j \cdot A_{\min,k,n_t+1-j}^t(t)] \cdot H(R - [R]_{\text{cr}}) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_t} A_{\min,k,j}^t(t) \cdot [1 - H(R - [R]_{\text{cr}})] \quad (20)$$

234 where n_t is the number of tension bars; $[R]_{\text{cr}}$ is the critical value of corrosion non-uniformity
 235 factor 1.3 [43]; $A_{\min,k,j}^t(t)$ is the minimum cross-sectional area (mm^2) of the j -th tension bar in
 236 ascending order in the k -th zone ($A_{\min,k,1}^t(t) < A_{\min,k,2}^t(t) < \dots < A_{\min,k,n_t}^t(t)$); and $H(x)$ is the
 237 Heaviside function that equals 1 when the value inside parentheses ≥ 0 and 0 otherwise.

238 In addition, according to the classical truss models with a crack inclination angle of 45° ,

239 the shear bearing capacity $V_k(t)$ of any zone in the beam is given by Eq.(21) [11,12].

$$240 \quad V_k(t) = V_c + V_{s,k}(t) = 1.75/(\lambda_s + 1) \cdot f_t b h_0 + F_{A_v,k}(t) \cdot h_0 / s_v \quad (21)$$

241 where V_c and $V_{s,k}$ are denoted as the contributions of concrete and stirrup components on shear
242 capacity, respectively; f_t is the concrete tensile strength; λ_s is the shear-to-span ratio; $F_{A_v,k}(t)$ is
243 the vertical tensile capacity of stirrup bars under the k -th zone at time t . Since only the vertical
244 parts of the stirrup bars are considered for computing the shear capacity of RC beams, $F_{A_v,k}(t)$
245 can be calculated by summing the tensile capacities of the vertical parts of all stirrups legs, as
246 shown in Eq.(22).

$$247 \quad F_{A_v,k}(t) = f_{yv0} A_k^s(t) = f_{yv0} \sum_{w=1}^{n_{sv}} A_{\min,k,w}^s(t) \quad (22)$$

248 in which f_{yv0} is the yield strength of uncorroded stirrup bars; n_{sv} is the number of stirrup legs;
249 $A_k^s(t)$ is the equivalent cross-sectional area sum of stirrup bars in the k -th zone; and $A_{\min,k,w}^s(t)$
250 ($k=1, 2, \dots, m$; $w=1, 2, \dots, n_{sv}$) is the minimum cross-sectional area (mm^2) of the w -th stirrup bar
251 of the k -th zone. Eqs.(18)-(22) are directly applied to calculate $M_{u,k}$, and $V_{u,k}$ for each zone by
252 the mechanical properties of the reinforcement and concrete and the cross-sectional areas of
253 steel bars.

254 **3.2.2. Finite element model of RC structures**

255 Although the models from Section 3.2.1 provide an estimate of the mechanical capacity of RC
256 beams over time, such predictions might be inaccurate and need modifications in the
257 performance assessment of RC beams, since the mechanical properties of steel and concrete
258 and their interaction are not adequately considered. A FEM for corroded RC beams is employed
259 to address such a concern, which could comprehensively consider realistic geometry and
260 mechanical properties [17]. The total strain-based crack model is used for the concrete
261 constitutive model [45]. As illustrated in Fig.3a, the tensile concrete stress increases linearly

262 before reaching the ultimate tensile strength and then drops following a tension-softening model
 263 developed by Hordijk [46]. The compressive concrete stress increases/decreases following
 264 parabolic curves [47]. In addition, as shown in Fig.3b, a corrosion degree-based trilinear
 265 constitutive model of corroded steel bars is adopted [48], where the elastic modulus E_{s0} , actual
 266 yield strength f_{y0} , and ultimate strength of corroded steel bar f_{t0} remain unchanged [49,50].
 267 Besides, hardened strain ε_{shc} and ultimate strain ε_{suc} decrease with the corrosion degree, which
 268 could be expressed by Eqs. (23) and (24) [51–53].

$$269 \quad \varepsilon_{shc} = \begin{cases} f_{y0}/E_{s0} + (\varepsilon_{sh0} - f_{y0}/E_{s0})(1 - \eta_s/\eta_{s,cr}), & \eta_s \leq \eta_{s,cr} \\ \varepsilon_{syc} = f_{y0}/E_{s0}, & \eta_s > \eta_{s,cr} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

$$270 \quad \varepsilon_{suc} = \exp(-2.501\eta_s) \varepsilon_{su0} \quad (24)$$

271 where $\eta_{s,cr}$ is the critical corrosion degree [12,54]; and ε_{sh0} and ε_{su0} are the hardened strain and
 272 ultimate strain of non-corroded steel bars. Moreover, different from the analytical models in
 273 Section 3.2.1, the bond-slip constitutive model is considered in FEM by directly assigning it to
 274 the interface between steel bar and concrete, as shown in Fig.3c. The bond stress τ of corroded
 275 steel bars versus slip s could be written as [55]

$$276 \quad \tau = \begin{cases} \tau_1 (s/l_1)^{0.3}, & 0 \leq s < s_0 \\ (s-s_0)/(s_1-s_0) \cdot (1-0.7) \cdot \tau_{max} + 0.7 \cdot \tau_{max}, & s_0 \leq s < s_1 \\ (s-s_1)/(s_1-s_2) \cdot (1-0.3) \cdot \tau_{max} + \tau_{max}, & s_1 \leq s < s_2 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

$$\tau_1 = 2.57 f_c^{0.5}, s_0 = 0.15c_0 (\alpha_{bond} \tau_{max} / \tau_1)^{1/0.3}, s_1 = 0.15c_0 \exp[(1/0.3) \ln(\tau_{max} / \tau_1)] + 0.4 \ln(\tau_1 / \tau_{max})$$

277 where c_0 is the rib spacing; s_2 is $0.35c_0$, respectively; and τ_{max} is the maximum bond strength
 278 of RC beams, which could be evaluated by an empirical model [56]:

$$279 \quad \tau_{max} = (k_1 + k_2 \eta_{ave}) [0.55 + 0.24(c/d_t)] \sqrt{f_c} + 0.191 \cdot A_{sv} f_y / (s_v \cdot d_t) \quad (26)$$

280 where c is the concrete cover thickness; d_t is the diameter of the tension bar; A_{sv} is the cross-
 281 sectional area of stirrup bars; and k_1 and k_2 are the factors of the reduced contribution of concrete
 282 towards bond strength [57]. Given the geometric model, boundary conditions, constitutive

283 model, and loading pattern, the FEM can be used to capture the comprehensive information
 284 (i.e., strains and stress of reinforcement and concrete, mid-span deflection, and reaction loads
 285 at supports) at each load step. Furthermore, the critical external loads at the serviceability limit
 286 state (SLS) $P_{FEM,si}$ ($i=1,2$), and ultimate limit state (ULS) $P_{FEM,u}$ could be calculated according
 287 to the reaction loads and corresponding mechanical information [17]. The failure mode F_{mod} of
 288 RC beams can be determined according to the sequence of the individual events: stirrup bars
 289 breaking, tension bars breaking, and concrete crushing, where the first one is regarded as a shear
 290 failure $F_{mod}=0$ and the latter two are considered to be flexural failures $F_{mod}=1$ [17].

291 3.3.Time-dependent reliability analysis

292 For time-dependent reliability analysis, the first step is to establish the performance functions
 293 $g(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t)$ given different limit states, including ultimate limit state (ULS) and two serviceability
 294 limit states (SLS): SLS1 (0.05 mm loading concrete crack [58]) and SLS2 (1 mm severe loading
 295 concrete crack [59]), and corresponding to three critical loads, i.e., P_u , P_{s1} , and P_{s2} , respectively.

296 Taking ULS as an example, the performance function for P_u could be written as

$$297 \quad g_u(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) = P_u(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) - S(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) \quad (27)$$

298 in which $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is the vector containing all input variables; and $P_u(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t)$ and $S(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t)$ are the ultimate
 299 capacities and external load at a given time instant t and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, respectively. Accordingly,
 300 considering the first passage issue, the time-dependent failure probability $p_{f,u}(t)$ could be
 301 described as the probability that $g_u(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t)$ reaches the critical value within a given time interval
 302 $[0, t]$, i.e., Eq.(28).

$$303 \quad p_{f,u}(t) = \Pr\{g_u(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \tau) \leq 0, \tau \in [0, t]\} \quad (28)$$

304 Similarly, regarding the two SLSs, their performance function $g_{si}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t)$ ($i=1$ and 2) and
 305 corresponding time-dependent probability $p_{f,si}(t)$ could be expressed by Eqs. (29) and (30).

$$306 \quad g_{si}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) = P_{si}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) - S(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t), (i=1,2) \quad (29)$$

307
$$p_{s,i}(t) = \Pr \{g_{s,i}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \tau) \leq 0, \tau \in [0, t]\}, (i = 1, 2) \quad (30)$$

308 The essential step of solving $p_{f,u}(t)$ and $p_{s,i}(t)$ is to accurately capture the probabilistic
 309 distribution information for the critical external loads via the models in Section 3.2. Although
 310 FEM is potent in accurately calculating the mechanical information of RC structures, it is not
 311 as straightforward as analytical models in estimating the capacities of RC structures over time.
 312 Therefore, inspired by previous studies [29,60], a suboptimal strategy is applied to apply
 313 adjustment coefficients (α_{s1} , α_{s2} , and α_u) to modify the results of the analytical models based on
 314 the FEM results.

315
$$\alpha_{s_i}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) = P_{FEM,si}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) / P_{ana}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t), \alpha_u(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) = P_{FEM,u}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) / P_{ana}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t), (i = 1, 2) \quad (31)$$

316 where $P_{FEM,si}$ is the critical load computed from FEM given the limit state, input variables, and
 317 time t ; and P_{ana} is the ultimate load computed based on the analytical models as

318
$$P_{ana}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) = \min \{P_{M_u}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t), P_{V_u}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t)\} \quad (32)$$

319 where P_{M_u} and P_{V_u} are the loading capacities of flexural and shear capacities based on the $M_{u,k}$,
 320 and $V_{u,k}$ ($k=1, 2, \dots, m$) and the loading pattern of RC beams. According to Eqs. (31) and (32),
 321 given the adjustment coefficients, the adjusted loading capacities subject to different limit states
 322 could be expressed by Eq. (33).

323
$$P_u(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) = \alpha_u(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) \cdot P_{ana}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t), P_{s_i}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) = \alpha_{s_i}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) \cdot P_{ana}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, t) \quad (33)$$

324 4. Bayesian network developments

325 4.1. Static and Dynamic Bayesian networks

326 A BN is applied to represent a joint probability distribution concerning a set of random variables
 327 (called nodes in BN) $X_{1:n_{bn}} = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_{bn}}\}$ (n_{bn} is the number of nodes) and consists of two
 328 parts: a directed acyclic graph (DAG) with vertices and edges corresponding to nodes X_{bn} and
 329 their dependencies; and the probability distribution information of all nodes.

330 Generally, two types of BN exist, i.e., static BN (SBN) and dynamic BN (DBN). The

331 former contains only a one-time slice for time-independent variables, and the latter is adopted
 332 to depict the time dependencies among variables, e.g., c_{bar} , i_{corr} , and P_u . DBN contains a series
 333 of time-slice BNs with a set of random variables $X_{1:n_{bn}}^i = \{X_1^i, X_2^i, \dots, X_{n_{bn}}^i\}$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, T$) at
 334 different time steps [28]. Within DBNs, the joint probability distribution $P(X_{1:n_{bn}}^1, \dots, X_{1:n_{bn}}^T)$ of
 335 all nodes over time T is denoted as $P(X_{1:n_{bn}}^{1:T})$, expressed by Eq.(34) via adopting the Markov
 336 assumption [30]:

$$337 \quad P(X_{1:n_{bn}}^{1:T}) = \prod_{i=1}^{T-1} P(X_{1:n_{bn}}^{i+1} | X_{1:n_{bn}}^i) \quad (34)$$

338 where $P(X_{1:n_{bn}}^{i+1} | X_{1:n_{bn}}^i)$ denotes the conditional probability distribution at the $i+1$ -th time slice
 339 given the probability information of nodes at the i -th time slice. Due to Markov's assumption
 340 and Eq. (34), T time slices of DBN can be built by unrolling the first two time slices of DBN,
 341 effectively reducing the difficulty of DBN modeling.

342 For exact inference, only discrete random variables are concerned. To perform exact
 343 inference for continuous random variables, discretization is implemented. Besides, the
 344 conditional probability mass functions (PMF) of all nodes are expressed by the conditional
 345 probability table (CPT). The procedure of node discretization and CPT computation are outlined
 346 in Appendix A1 [2]. Then, supposing a n_{bn} nodes of SBN and given an evidence combination
 347 $y_{1:n_2} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n_2})$ of inspection nodes Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_{n_2} (n_2 is the number of inspection nodes), the
 348 joint PMF of residual n_1 (i.e., $n_{bn} - n_2$) nodes X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_1} could be expressed by

$$349 \quad P(X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_{n_1} = x_{n_1} | Y_1 = y_1, \dots, Y_{n_2} = y_{n_2}) = \frac{\prod_i P(y_i | \text{Pa}(y_i)) \prod_j P(x_j | \text{Pa}(x_j))}{\sum_{x_1, \dots, x_{n_1}} \prod_i P(y_i | \text{Pa}(y_i)) \prod_j P(x_j | \text{Pa}(x_j))}, i=1, \dots, n_2, j=1, \dots, n_1 \quad (35)$$

350 where $\text{Pa}(y_i)$ is the set of parent nodes of Y_i . For T time slices of DBN, supposing a set of
 351 evidence combinations at all time slices $\{y_{1:m}^1, \dots, y_{1:m}^T\} = \{y_1^1, \dots, y_{n_2}^1, \dots, y_1^T, \dots, y_{n_2}^T\}$, the joint

352 PMF of residual n_1 (i.e., $n_{bn} - n_2$) nodes could be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
& P\left(X_{1:n_1}^1 = x_{1:n_1}^1, \dots, X_{1:n_1}^T = x_{1:n_1}^T \mid Y_{1:n_2}^1 = y_{1:n_2}^1, \dots, Y_{1:n_2}^T = y_{1:n_2}^T\right) = \\
& \frac{\prod_{u,v} P\left(y_v^u \mid \text{Pa}\left(y_v^u\right)\right) \prod_{p,q} P\left(x_q^p \mid \text{Pa}\left(x_q^p\right)\right)}{\sum_{x_{1:n_1}^1, \dots, x_{1:n_1}^T} \prod_{u,v} P\left(y_v^u \mid \text{Pa}\left(y_v^u\right)\right) \prod_{p,q} P\left(x_q^p \mid \text{Pa}\left(x_q^p\right)\right)}, u=1, \dots, T, v=1, \dots, n_2, p=1, \dots, T, q=1, \dots, n_1
\end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

354 where $\text{Pa}(y_q^p)$ is the set of parent nodes of Y_q^p . Evidence that is a series of definite values is
355 called hard evidence. Correspondingly, if the evidence obtained for the inspection nodes is a
356 series of distributions, it is called uncertain evidence or soft evidence [61,62]. Denoting the
357 inspection status of node Y_i and Y_v^u in SBN and DBN as y_{i0} and y_{vs}^u , respectively, $P(Y_i = y_{is})$ and
358 $P(Y_v^u = y_{vs}^u)$ are the probabilities of the s -th status of Y_i and Y_v^u . Then, Eqs.(35) and (36) could
359 be rewritten to Eqs. (37) and (38), respectively.

$$\begin{aligned}
& P\left(X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_{n_1} = x_{n_1} \mid Y_1 = y_{10}, \dots, Y_{n_2} = y_{n_20}\right) = \\
& \frac{\sum_{y_{1:n_2s}} \prod_j P\left(x_j \mid \text{Pa}\left(x_j\right)\right) \prod_i \left[P\left(y_i \mid \text{Pa}\left(y_i\right)\right) P\left(Y_i = y_{is}\right) \right]}{\sum_{x_1, \dots, x_{n_1}, y_{1:n_2s}} \prod_j P\left(x_j \mid \text{Pa}\left(x_j\right)\right) \prod_i \left[P\left(y_i \mid \text{Pa}\left(y_i\right)\right) P\left(Y_i = y_{is}\right) \right]}, i=1, \dots, n_2, j=1, \dots, n_1, s=1, 2, \dots
\end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& P\left(X_{1:n_1}^1 = x_{1:n_1}^1, \dots, X_{1:n_1}^T = x_{1:n_1}^T \mid Y_{1:n_2}^1 = y_{1:n_2}^1, \dots, Y_{1:n_2}^T = y_{1:n_2}^T\right) = \\
& \frac{\sum_{y_{1:n_2s}^1, \dots, y_{1:n_2s}^T} \prod_{p,q} P\left(x_q^p \mid \text{Pa}\left(x_q^p\right)\right) \prod_{u,v} \left[P\left(y_{vs}^u \mid \text{Pa}\left(y_{vs}^u\right)\right) \cdot P\left(Y_v^u = y_{vs}^u\right) \right]}{\sum_{x_{1:n_1}^1, \dots, x_{1:n_1}^T, y_{1:n_2s}^1, \dots, y_{1:n_2s}^T} \prod_{p,q} P\left(x_q^p \mid \text{Pa}\left(x_q^p\right)\right) \prod_{u,v} \left[P\left(y_{vs}^u \mid \text{Pa}\left(y_{vs}^u\right)\right) \cdot P\left(Y_v^u = y_{vs}^u\right) \right]}, \\
& u=1, \dots, T, v=1, \dots, n_2, p=1, \dots, T, q=1, \dots, n_1, s=1, 2, \dots
\end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

362 The above BN inference is achieved by a frontier algorithm, including a smoothing
363 strategy for both forward and backward operators to reduce the time complexity of DBN
364 inference [28]. However, as the number of time slices and nodes increases, the computational
365 burden may increase dramatically, and some studies suggested reducing the links and number
366 of discretized states in BN analysis [19,20]. Even so, integrating all the physical models and
367 random variables in Section 3 to establish a giant DBN and implementing BN inference still is
368 a formidable challenge.

369 4.2. Mixed Bayesian network for reliability analysis of RC structures

370 As stated in Section 4.1, it is more challenging to build DBNs directly due to many parameters
371 and computational models. Besides, different from the analytical mechanical model, it is
372 challenging to consider temporal correlation in FEM evaluation. Thus, apart from DBN, it is
373 still necessary to build SBN to perform the information updating of adjustment coefficients (α_{s1} ,
374 α_{s2} , and α_u) at each time instant. To realize a comprehensive reliability analysis of RC beams,
375 an MBN involving multiple sub-BNs (DBNs and SBNs) for the integrated reliability analysis
376 of RC beams, as shown in Fig.4. Each node in the MBN represents a sub-BN and its output
377 variables, such as i_{corr} , Δr , and P_{Mu} , where the 'blue nodes' represent DBNs and the 'white nodes'
378 represent SBNs. For instance, ' i_{corr} ' and ' Δr ' represent DBNs for durability assessment; ' α_x ' and
379 ' F_{mod} ' are SBNs for adjustment factors and failure modes of FEM. Simultaneously, these output
380 variables are shared nodes of two adjacent sub-BNs since they can work as pinch point variables
381 to connect adjacent sub-BNs. For instance, given the inspection results of corrosion-induced
382 crack width ω in the DBNs of ' i_{corr} ' and ' Δr ', the PMFs of the pinch point variables i_{corr} and Δr
383 can be updated and then work as soft evidence for the nodes of i_{corr} and Δr in the DBNs of ' P_{Mu} '
384 and ' P_{Vu} ' and the SBNs of ' α_x ' and ' F_{mod} '. Similarly, the updated PMFs of the P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} nodes
385 of ' P_{Mu} ' and ' P_{Vu} ' can be used as soft evidence for the DBN updating of ' g_x '. The node
386 discretization, CPT computation, and inference process of MBN are consistent with SBN and
387 DBN in Section 4.1. The primary merit of MBN is that there is no need to oversimplify any
388 sub-BNs in the model deliberately, and the critical physical information of each BN is retained
389 as much as possible, making MBN potentially more accurate relative to a simplified BN. In
390 addition, due to the modular feature of MBN, the structure of each sub-BN and the probabilistic
391 information of the nodes can be conveniently replaced according to the requirements.

392 According to MBN in Fig.4 and models in Section 3, other sub-BNs are introduced in the

393 following. An SBN based on FEM is built to introduce the information for the variables α_x and
394 F_{mod} , as illustrated in Fig.5. Other critical input variables, such as i_{corr} , Δr , A_k^t ($k=1, 2, \dots, m$),
395 and A_k^s ($k=1, 2, \dots, m$), are also extracted as nodes for this SBN. Moreover, the parent-child
396 relationship of these nodes is determined, e.g., A_k^t is a child node of i_{corr} and Δr but a parent
397 node of α_x , as shown in Fig.5. Given the updating information of i_{corr} and Δr at any time instant,
398 this SBN could provide the updating information of α_x and F_{mod} accordingly. Furthermore, the
399 available studies prove that not every cross-section contributes to the mechanical properties of
400 the corroded RC beams [17]. Therefore, for the sake of simplicity, the number of A_k^t and A_k^s
401 investigated in Fig.5 can be limited based on the sensitivity analysis results. Besides, other sub-
402 BNs, including durability assessment, analytical capacity calculation, and reliability assessment,
403 are established via DBNs, as presented in Fig.6a, b, and c, where arc-shaped dashed arrows
404 indicate the time dependence between adjacent time slices. Also, similar to Fig.5, the numbers
405 of A_k^t and A_k^s investigated could be appropriately reduced by the sensitivity analysis results.
406 Besides, for the DBN relating to time-dependent reliability analysis (Fig.6c), the probabilistic
407 information of some input variables needs to be captured by the SBN of FEM in each time slice.

408 5. Illustrative examples

409 5.1. Description

410 To illustrate and study the efficiency of the developed framework, a simply supported RC beam
411 with a cross-section of 150×300 mm is assumed to be located on the west coast of the Yellow
412 Sea since 2010, as displayed in Fig.2 [1]. The parameters of the geometry and reinforcement
413 layout of the beam are listed in Table 1. Regarding the environmental and durability assessment,
414 the parameters for environmental models $f(ec, t)$ were obtained from previous studies [1,63].
415 Fig.7 presents an example of the variation of environmental parameters, including temperature
416 T , relative humidity RH, and chloride deposition C_{surf} , assuming $ec = 2^\circ\text{C}$. As shown, this

417 example accounts for the periodicity, time dependence, and nonlinearity within the variations
 418 of environmental parameters. In addition, the distribution types and parameters of isolated
 419 parent nodes in all sub-BNs (Figs.5 and 6) are listed in Table 2. The following sections focus
 420 on building MBN and presenting the time-dependent reliability analysis by integrating the
 421 inspection results. The former is described in Section 5.2, and the latter will be presented in
 422 Sections 5.3 and 5.4.

423 Table 1 Geometry parameters and reinforcement of the studied RC beams

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
Total length l	5400 mm	Effective length l_{ef}	5000 mm
Effective section height h_0	275 mm	Stirrup spacing s_v	250 mm
Section width b	150 mm	Number of tension bars n_t	3
Initial diameter of tension bars d_{t0}	20 mm	Number of compression bars n_c	2
Initial diameter of compression bars d_{c0}	12 mm	Number of stirrup bars n_{sv}	2
Initial diameter of stirrup bars d_{sv0}	6 mm	Number of zones m	20

424 Table 2 Distribution types and values of parent nodes in sub-BNs

Parameters	Distribution	μ	δ	Ref
Characteristic exposure conditions ec (°C)	Uniform	0	3.5	[1]
A baseline of chloride deposition c_{surf0} (wt% of cement)	Gaussian*	0.65	0.1	[1]
Reference coefficient of chloride diffusion D_0 (10^{-11} m ² /s)	Lognormal	1.6	0.1	[64]
Cover thickness c (mm)	Gaussian*	25	0.05	[65]
Critical chloride content c_{cr} (wt% of cement)	Lognormal	0.4	0.1	[14]
Resistance of concrete cover R_c (k Ω)	Lognormal	25	0.1	[35]
Compressive strength of concrete f_c (MPa)	Gaussian*	25	0.15	[14]
Elastic modulus of reinforcement (MPa)	Gaussian*	2×10^5	0.02	[66]
Yield strength of longitudinal bars (MPa)	Gaussian*	360	0.05	[67]
Yield strength of stirrup bars (MPa)	Gaussian*	220	0.05	[66]

425 Note: μ and δ are the lower and upper bounds for the uniform distribution value, while μ and δ are the mean and coefficient of variation (COV)
 426 for other distributions; * means that the variable is truncated at 0.

427 5.2.MBN establishment

428 Before building the MBN for the RC beam, some preparations must be completed to obtain a
 429 priori information on all nodes in MBNs, and their probabilistic information is captured from
 430 representative samples. To select representative samples, the point selection method from
 431 existing studies [2,68] is employed to generate 610 representative samples in terms of the
 432 distribution information on isolated parent nodes in Table 2. Given the values of isolated parent
 433 nodes for each representative sample, the values of all other nodes could be computed based on
 434 the deterioration models mentioned in Sections 3.1-3.2. To reduce the analysis burden, the
 435 MBN needs to be simplified accordingly by appropriately reducing the number of time slices,

436 nodes, and links. For demonstration purposes and consistency with existing studies [2], the time
437 intervals and slices are preset to 3 years and 18, and the number of discrete statuses for each
438 node is set to 8 except for some binary node g_x (g_{s1} , g_{s2} , and g_u).

439 On the other hand, considering corrosion non-uniformity, RC beams are divided into m
440 zones with a large number of random variables associated with the cross-sectional area of the
441 corroded reinforcement (A_k^t and A_k^s , $k=1, 2, \dots, m$) (Section 3.2), which also brings a burden on
442 the MBN inferential analysis. Thus, sensitivity analysis is implemented to investigate the
443 contributions of each spatial zone to the mechanical performance of RC beams. As illustrated
444 in Fig.8, the probability of ULS occurrence in each spatial zone is calculated based on the results
445 of 610 representative samples over 50 years. Both Fig.8a and b show that the flexural failure
446 events are concentrated at the mid-span of the RC beam, while the shear damage events are
447 concentrated near the supports of the RC beam. Such a phenomenon is consistent with
448 mechanical behavior [10,69]. Fig.8 also demonstrates that the spatial distribution of the ULS
449 occurrences of the analytical model differs from FEM results so that the sub-BNs are simplified
450 in different ways. Among the sub-BNs associated with the analytical model (Fig.6b), the 9th to
451 12th zones (i.e., A_9^t to A_{12}^t) are of interest for flexural failure, and the 1st and 20th zones (i.e.,
452 A_1^s and A_{20}^s) are of interest for shear failure. Regarding the sub-BNs of the FEM (Fig.5), the
453 8th to 13th zones (i.e., A_8^t to A_{13}^t) are of interest for flexural failure; the 1st to 4th zones (i.e.,
454 A_1^s to A_4^s) and 17th to 20th zones (i.e., A_{17}^s to A_{20}^s) are of interest for shear failure. According
455 to Appendix A.1, all nodes in MBNs are discretized into discrete nodes, and their CPTs are
456 computed accordingly. Besides, it is worth noting that the pinch-point variables in MBN own
457 two CPTs since they simultaneously serve as parent and child nodes in adjacent sub-BNs.

458 **5.3.Inference results**

459 Once the MBN is established, the following task is to infer and evaluate the performance of RC

460 beams. Supposing the probability of detection (PoD) equals one, the width ω of corrosion-
461 induced concrete crack could be detected at several inspection instants (i.e., 3, 12, 21, 30, and
462 39 years), and possible inspection results of ω (mm) are supposed: $\omega_1 \in [0, 0.1]$, $\omega_2 \in [0.2,$
463 $0.3]$, and $\omega_3 \in [0.5, 0.6]$ [2]. The MBN was applied to infer critical parameters of the structural
464 performance of RC beams subjected to different inspections, such as the flexural and shear
465 capacity P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} , adjustment coefficients α_x , and limit state variable g_x . Since durability
466 assessments such as chloride content and corrosion rates c_{bar} and i_{corr} on the steel surface have
467 been explored in detail in a previous study [2], these will not be discussed again in this study.

468 5.3.1. PMF of critical nodes in MBN

469 To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed framework, some classical scenarios are
470 picked up to exhibit the a priori and a posteriori PMFs of critical parameters, as illustrated in
471 Fig.9. As shown, the 3rd year inspection of ω_2 affects the PMFs of all parameters over time,
472 while the 39th year inspection of ω_1 essentially has little effect on the PMFs before 39 years.
473 Also, compared to no inspection, the earlier inspection results in higher PMFs in the negative
474 axis direction for P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} , while the later inspection increases PMFs in the positive axis
475 direction. For instance, in Fig.9b and c, given the 3rd year inspection of ω_2 , the probability of
476 P_{Mu} in the range of 20.1 to 21.7 (kN) in 39 years increases by 241.7% compared to no inspection,
477 while that in the range of 23.3 to 24.8 decreases by 99%; the probability of P_{Vu} in the range of
478 19.2 to 20.6 (kN) increases by 644.0% while that in the range of 23.3 to 24.6 (kN) decreases by
479 99.1%. This result matches common sense, as wider cracks indicate higher corrosion and lower
480 load-bearing capacity and vice versa.

481 However, the scenario is slightly different for α_x . In 3 years, considering the 3rd year
482 inspection of ω_2 , the probability of α_1 in the range of 0.38 to 0.41 decreases by 32.5%, and that
483 in the range of 0.41 to 0.43 increases by 26.1%. In 21 years, the inspection has little effect on

484 the PMF of α_2 . Besides, in 39 years, considering the 3rd year inspection of ω_2 , the probability
 485 of α_u in the range of 0.88 to 0.94 increased by 43.7%, and that in the range of 0.94 to 0.99
 486 decreased by 30.1% - the vice versa for the 39th year inspection of ω_1 . Thus, the effects of
 487 inspection results on the adjustment coefficients of SLS might not be as significant as ULS. In
 488 addition, different from P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} , the adjustment ratio might not decrease with the corrosion
 489 degree for SLS. In the following, the influence of different test results on the mechanical
 490 capacity and the probability and mode of failure at different limit states are discussed in further
 491 detail.

492 5.3.2. Effects of inspection results on mechanical capacities

493 This subsection investigates the influences of different inspection results on P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} . To
 494 facilitate the comparisons of different scenarios, the mean and standard deviation (STD) of
 495 discrete nodes are used here [2], which are calculated by Eqs. (39) and (40), respectively.

$$496 \quad E(x) = 0.5 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_x} (d_k + d_{k+1}) \cdot P_x(k) \quad (39)$$

$$497 \quad \sqrt{D(x)} = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^{n_x} (0.5 \cdot (d_k + d_{k+1}) - E(x))^2 \cdot P_x(k)} \quad (40)$$

498 in which x is the target node; $[d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{n_x+1}]$ is the discretization scheme of x ; and $P_x(k)$ is the
 499 PMF of x at its k -th interval. Fig.10 illustrates the mean and STD of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} for different
 500 inspection results, where the mean value of P_{Mu} over time is higher than P_{Vu} , but the STD of
 501 P_{Mu} is lower than P_{Vu} . In Fig.10a and b, the mean values keep decreasing with time, and those
 502 of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} with the 3rd year inspection of ω_2 decrease the fastest among all scenarios, with
 503 maximum reductions of 8.8% and 8.7% for P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} compared to no inspection. In addition,
 504 for the 21st-year inspection, the mean values of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} decreased much more slowly than
 505 in other scenarios, with a maximum increase of 6.5% and 5.4% for P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} compared to
 506 no inspection. Moreover, compared to other years of inspection, P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} of the 39th-year

507 inspection are closer to no inspection. The above results indicate that early inspection of
508 moderate-width cracks significantly reduces the mean value of the load capacity. Also, small
509 cracks observed at the middle to late service life dramatically increase the mean value of the
510 load capacity because large cracks are expected after 21 years of exposure.

511 On the other hand, the STD of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} (Fig.10c and d) indicate that STD values
512 initially increase and then decrease. The peak of STD depends on the inspection results. For
513 instance, given the 21st-year inspection of ω_2 , the STDs of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} peak in 6 and 9 years,
514 respectively, 4.8% and 0.64% higher than no inspection, while given that of ω_1 , both the STDs
515 of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} peak in 51 years, 5.7% and 10.2% higher than no inspection. Such results
516 indicate that, given the inspection time, the larger concrete crack could advance the STD peak
517 of load capacity. In addition, given the 3rd year inspection of ω_2 , the STDs of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} peak
518 in 3 and 6 years, 3.7% higher and 1.3% lower than no inspection, while given the 39th year
519 inspection of ω_2 , both the STDs of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} peak in 33 years, 5.1% and 1.1% lower than
520 no inspection. Therefore, given the inspection results for concrete crack width, the earlier the
521 inspection occurs, the earlier the STD of load capacity reaches its peak.

522 5.3.3. Effects of inspection results on failure probabilities

523 This subsection investigates the influences of inspection results on failure probabilities
524 considering different limit states, as illustrated in Fig.11-13. For SLS, the effects of inspection
525 on failure probability are not as significant as ultimate for ULS. For SLS1 (Eq.(30) with 0.05
526 mm limit cracks size), $p_{f,s1}$ ranges from 0.65 to 1 for all scenarios. Meanwhile, Fig.11 shows
527 that the differences among different scenarios are limited and decrease rapidly over time until
528 it is below 1% after 6 years. Among the displayed scenarios with inspection, the highest $p_{f,s1}$
529 could be found under the 3rd-year inspection of ω_2 5.2% higher than no inspection, followed
530 by the 12th-year inspection of ω_3 (4.8% higher than no inspection) and the lowest in the 30th-

531 year inspection of ω_3 (1.4% higher than no inspection). Such a result might suggest that the
532 occurrence probability of a 0.05 mm loading crack is relatively high in this case and therefore
533 $p_{f,s1}$ is not sensitive to the inspection results of corrosion-induced cracks.

534 Furthermore, for SLS2, Fig.12 illustrates that given the inspection results of ω_2 , $p_{f,s2}$ is
535 ranging from 10^{-3} to 0.04, and $p_{f,s2}$ varies nonlinearly over time. For instance, given the 3rd-
536 year and 12th-year inspection of ω_2 , $p_{f,s2}$ is initially 12.7% and 5.1% higher, 30.2% and 11.8%
537 lower but eventually 19.1% and 9.7% higher than no inspection, respectively. However, for the
538 30th-year inspection of ω_2 , $p_{f,s2}$ is maximum 13.5% higher than no inspection before 45 years
539 but 3.7% lower than no inspection until the end of service life. The above results indicate that
540 the occurrence probability of a 1 mm loading crack is more sensitive to inspection results of
541 corrosion-induced crack than that of a 0.05 mm loading crack. Besides, the influences of
542 corrosion-induced cracks on 1 mm loading cracks appear of particular nonlinearity and
543 hysteresis.

544 On the other hand, for the ultimate limit state, Fig.13 shows that $p_{f,u}$ for all scenarios ranges
545 from 2×10^{-5} to 0.035 all over the service life, and the effects of inspection results on $p_{f,u}$ are
546 dramatic. For instance, given the 3rd year inspection of ω_2 and 12th year inspection of ω_3 , $p_{f,u}$
547 is 506% and 530% higher than no inspection. Such a result demonstrates that a high width of
548 corrosion-induced crack detected early in service life could significantly impair structural safety.
549 In addition, given the inspections of crack width, $p_{f,u}$ decreases with the inspection time. For
550 instance, $p_{f,u}$ with a 3rd-year inspection of ω_1 is maximum 8.2% lower than no inspection, and
551 $p_{f,u}$ with a 30th-year inspection of ω_1 is maximum 63.8% lower than no inspection. Besides,
552 $p_{f,u}$ with the 12th-year inspection of ω_2 is maximum 290% higher than no inspection, while $p_{f,u}$
553 with the 30th-year inspection of ω_2 is maximum 30.7% higher and 4.3% lower than no
554 inspection after 51 and 21 years, respectively. Thus, a smaller width of corrosion-induced

555 cracks detected when approaching the end of service life implies better structural reliability and
556 safety.

557 **5.3.4. Effects of inspection results on failure modes**

558 In this subsection, the inspection effects on failure modes are further investigated, as displayed
559 in Fig.14. Considering no inspection, the probability of shear failure after 3 years is basically
560 the same as that of flexural failure and increases with time, exceeding that of flexural failure by
561 123.8% after 27 years. In addition, given the 12th and 30th-year inspection results of ω_1 , the
562 probabilities of flexural and shear failure initially do not change compared to no inspection
563 (Fig.14a). After 27 years, the probability of shear failure decreases by 7.4% and 25%,
564 respectively, and that of flexural failure increases by 16.6% and 56.8%, respectively (Fig.14b),
565 compared to no inspection. Therefore, the later the inspection occurs, the higher the probability
566 of flexural failure, given the inspection results of small crack widths.

567 Furthermore, given the 12th and 30th-year inspection results of ω_3 , the probability of
568 shear failure increases by 39.0% and 3.1% after 3 years, respectively, while the probability of
569 flexural failure decreases by 42.6% and 3.4% after 3 years, compared to no inspection. Also,
570 the probability of shear failure dramatically increases by 23.5% and 23.4% after 48 years,
571 respectively, while the probability of flexural failure decreases by 81.6% and 81.3% after 48
572 years, compared to no inspection. Thus, inspection results for large crack widths lead to a
573 significant increase in shear failure probability, which is advanced by when cracks are detected
574 during the earlier inspection time.

575 **5.4. Other effects**

576 In this section, the effects of other factors, e.g., exposure condition ec , and models of the
577 environment and chloride transport on reliability estimation, are further discussed. For
578 convenience, the probabilities of shear and flexural failure are directly compared. They are

579 calculated by multiplying the failure probability of the corresponding limit states by the
 580 probability of failure mode over time, i.e., Eq.(41).

$$581 \quad p_{f,M}(t) = p_{f,u}(t) \cdot \Pr(F_{\text{mod}}(t)=0|\text{fail}), p_{f,V}(t) = p_{f,u}(t) \cdot \Pr(F_{\text{mod}}(t)=1|\text{fail}) \quad (41)$$

582 where $\Pr(F_{\text{mod}}(t)=0|\text{fail})$ and $\Pr(F_{\text{mod}}(t)=1|\text{fail})$ are the probabilities of flexural and shear failure,
 583 respectively.

584 For exposure conditions, two ec ($^{\circ}\text{C}$): $ec_1 \in [0, 0.6]$ and $ec_2 \in [2.9, 3.5]$ are considered to
 585 study the low and high level of ec and their effects on reliability estimation for no inspection
 586 and 21-th year inspection of ω_2 , as illustrated in Fig.15a and b. As shown, the effects of
 587 inspection results on $p_{f,M}$ are nonlinear, where $p_{f,M}$ firstly increases with time and then drops in
 588 15 to 21 years but then rises in the rest of service life. For instance, given the 21-th year
 589 inspection of ω_2 , the $p_{f,M}$ is initially 3.9% to 9.0% higher than no inspection before 15 years
 590 but 15.5% to 33.7% lower for the rest of service life. Besides, the effects of ec on $p_{f,M}$ are also
 591 nonlinear, and the $p_{f,M}$ for given ec_1 and ec_2 gradually exceeds that of no given ec . For instance,
 592 given ec_1 and no inspection, the $p_{f,M}$ is about 0.25% to 4.6% lower before 9 years but 3.6% to
 593 32.0% higher for the rest of service life, compared to no given ec . Besides, given ec_2 , $p_{f,M}$ is
 594 about 7.2% to 32.6% higher than no given ec .

595 Moreover, considering the 21-th year inspection of ω_2 and given ec_1 , the $p_{f,M}$ is about 3.3%
 596 to 11.7 % lower before 21 years to 8.0% higher than no given ec at the end of service life, while
 597 given ec_2 , $p_{f,M}$ is about 11.2 % higher than no given ec but 14.0% lower in 21 years, and rising
 598 to 27.3% higher at the end of service life. Although the effects of ec on flexural failure
 599 probability are complicated at the mid-service life, a higher level of ec results in higher growth
 600 in flexural failure probability near the end of service life. In contrast to $p_{f,M}$, considering no
 601 inspection, $p_{f,V}$ with given ec_1 and ec_2 is about 1.0% to 13.2% lower than no given ec at most
 602 times. Meanwhile, considering the 21-th year inspection of ω_2 and no given ec , $p_{f,V}$ is 2.4% to

603 175.6% higher than that without inspection, while $p_{f,V}$ with ec_1 is 2.2% to 11.6% lower but that
604 with ec_2 is 1.6% to 9.4% higher than no given ec . The above results suggest that inspection
605 results might significantly affect shear failure probability more than ec .

606 On the other hand, Fig.15c and d present the $p_{f,M}$ and $p_{f,V}$ subject to constant environment
607 and one-dimensional (1D) chloride transport. It can be seen that both the $p_{f,M}$ and $p_{f,V}$ of constant
608 environment and 1D chloride transport are lower than those of time-varying environment and
609 2D chloride transport (original case). Besides, given the 21-th year inspection of ω_2 , $p_{f,V}$
610 significantly increases beyond without inspection, while $p_{f,M}$ initially decreases but then rises.

611 However, for 1D chloride transport, compared to no inspection, the $p_{f,M}$ with the 21-th year
612 inspection of ω_2 is 11% higher after 27 years and 65.5% higher at the end of service life. In
613 addition, compared to 2D chloride transport, $p_{f,M}$ and $p_{f,V}$ without inspection is 21.9% to 76.4%
614 lower, while the 21-th year inspection of ω_2 results in 13.3% to 93.7% decrease on $p_{f,M}$ and
615 $p_{f,V}$. Thus, as illustrated in Fig.15c and d, considering 1D chloride transport underestimates the
616 failure probability drastically. In addition, for the constant environment, compared to the time-
617 varying environment, $p_{f,M}$ and $p_{f,V}$ without inspection are about 22.2% to 95.0% lower while
618 considering the 21-th year inspection of ω_2 , $p_{f,M}$ and $p_{f,V}$ are about 26.7% and 17.8% higher
619 initially but 88.8% and 94.9% lower at the end of service life. Thus, it can be found that ignoring
620 the time-varying environment could decrease the probabilities of shear and flexural failure.
621 Therefore, it could be concluded that 2D chloride transport and the time-varying environment
622 affect the effects of inspection results on failure probability assessment.

623 6. Conclusions

624 This study developed an MBN-based framework for the reliability estimation of RC structures
625 subject to long-term environmental effects. This framework consists of three modules:
626 durability assessment, mechanical assessment, and reliability assessment, achieved by the

627 combination of SBN and DBN. The information between adjacent BN is transferred by
628 applying pinch points and soft evidence. The time-dependent reliability analysis for RC beams
629 under marine atmospheric environment is made as one case to illustrate the effectiveness of the
630 proposed framework, and the following conclusion can be drawn:

631 (1) Inference results of MBN prove that the proposed framework could use the results of
632 inspections to update the probabilistic distribution of time-dependent mechanical capacity,
633 FEM adjustment coefficients, and performance functions. The flexural and shear load capacity
634 negatively correlate with the corrosion-induced crack width, while the FEM adjustment
635 coefficient is nonlinearly related.

636 (2) For load capacities, results indicate that early inspection of medium-width cracks decreases
637 the mean values of load capacities by about 9% while the small-width cracks raise the mean
638 values of load capacities by about 5 to 6%. Also, the earlier inspection time and wider cracks
639 could advance the peak of STD for load capacities.

640 (3) Failure probabilities subject to different limit states suggest that the effects of inspection
641 on the failure probability of serviceability limit states are nonlinearly related to inspection
642 results and not as significant as those of the ultimate limit state. Given the inspection of
643 corrosion-induced cracks, compared to no inspection, the probability of a 0.05mm loading crack
644 is about 1% to 5% higher, and that of a 1 mm loading crack is about 5% to 13% higher initially
645 but then about 3% to 30% lower. Regarding ultimate limit states, an early inspection of the high
646 level of corrosion-induced cracks might dramatically increase the failure probability by about
647 500%, and later inspection of small corrosion-induced cracks might decrease the failure
648 probability by about 64%

649 (4) Failure mode analysis gives that the probabilities of shear failure and flexural failure are
650 positively and negatively correlated with the inspection results, respectively. Results show that

651 a later inspection result of small corrosion-induced cracks might increase the probability of
652 flexural failure mode by about 16% to 57% and decrease that of shear failure mode by about
653 7% to 25%. In addition, large corrosion-induced cracks significantly increase the probability of
654 shear failure mode by 3% to 39% and decrease that of flexural failure mode by about 3% to
655 81%.

656 (5) Sensitivity analysis results show that the effects of exposure conditions on the failure
657 probability of different failure modes are different and nonlinear. Given the small characteristics
658 value of exposure condition ec_1 , compared to no given ec , the failure probability of flexural
659 failure decreases by about 0.2% to 12% initially but then increases by 3.6% to 32%, while that
660 of shear failure reduces by about 2% to 12%. Given a large characteristic value of exposure
661 condition ec_2 , the failure probability of flexural failure increases by 7.2% to 33%, while that of
662 shear failure increase by 1.6% to 10%. Moreover, considering the constant environment and
663 one-dimensional chloride transport could significantly reduce the failure probabilities of shear
664 and flexural failure by about 13 to 94% and 22% to 95%, respectively. Thus, ignoring the effects
665 of the time-varying environment and two-dimensional chloride transport underestimate the
666 failure probability and overestimate the effects of inspection results on failure probability at the
667 early stage.

668 In summary, it is practical to use the proposed MBN framework for the reliability
669 assessment of RC structures developed. The proposed approach can integrate the inspection
670 data with the life-cycle design and management of RC infrastructure and dramatically mitigate
671 the uncertainty in the life-cycle assessment of corroding RC structures

672 **Appendix:**

673 *A1. Algorithms of Node discretization and CPT computation*

674 The node discretization and CPT computation are implemented based on the methods from [2].

675 Taking a DBN with a set of nodes $X_{1:n_{bn}}^i = \{X_1^i, X_2^i, \dots, X_{n_{bn}}^i\}$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, T$) as one example, the
676 procedures of node discretization are presented. For DBN, the node discretization of all nodes
677 remains unchanged over time slices. Thus, the corresponding discretization scheme of each
678 node X_j ($j = 1, \dots, n_{bn}$) could be represented as $D_{X_j} = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{m_{X_j}+1}]$ with m_{X_j} equal intervals.

679 For those isolated parent nodes (time-independent parent nodes) given the distribution
680 types and parameters (such as the variables in Table 2), their lower and upper bounds (d_1 and
681 $d_{m_{X_j}+1}$) could be preset, and their PMFs can be expressed by [70]:

$$682 \quad P_{X_j}(k) = F_{X_j}(d_{k+1}) - F_{X_j}(d_k), k = 1, \dots, m_{X_j} \quad (42)$$

683 where $F_{X_j}(\cdot)$ denotes the CDF of X_j . For other types of nodes (child nodes or time-dependent
684 parent nodes) without preset distribution functions, their lower d_1 and upper bounds $d_{m_{X_j}+1}$ can
685 be determined by the minimum and maximum values of these nodes in the N number of
686 representative samples [2]. It is essential to note that in MBN, although the CPTs of the pinch
687 point variables are different in the adjacent sub-BNs, their discretization schemes must be
688 consistent for soft evidence transfer and update. Furthermore, the CPT of other types of nodes
689 comes from the joint distribution of investigated nodes and their parent nodes. For the sake of
690 expression, other types of nodes are noted as $Z_{1:n_c}^i = \{Z_1^i, Z_2^i, \dots, Z_{n_c}^i\}$ (n_c is the number of nodes,
691 and their CPT could be computed through the following steps:

- 692 (1) The discrete number of Z_j^i is noted as $m_{Z_j^i}$, and parent nodes are marked as a collection set
693 $X_{\text{col}} = [X_b^i, \dots, X_e^i]$ (b and e denote the serial numbers of the parent nodes in topological order
694 from the beginning to the end of the sequence). For the first representative sample and the first
695 time slice, let $k = 1$ and $i = 1$. For other time slices, the Z_j^{i-1} is becomes the first parent node of
696 Z_j^i and X_{col} is revised as $[Z_j^{i-1}, X_b^i, \dots, X_e^i]$;
697 (2) Determine the state z_j^i of the k -th sample and the i -th time slice of Z_j^i (denoted as $Z_{j,k}^{[i]}$)
698 based on its discretization scheme $D_{Z_j^i}$;

699 (3) Determine the states of all parent nodes in topological order and store these states as $\mathbf{x}_{pa} =$
700 $[x_{pa,b}, \dots, x_{pa,e}]$ for the first time slice and $[z^{i-1}_j, x_{pa,b}, \dots, x_{pa,e}]$ for other time slices. Meanwhile,
701 calculate a state variable x_{temp} by Eq. (43);

$$702 \quad x_{temp} = \begin{cases} x_{pa,b} + \sum_{p=b+1}^e (x_{pa,p} - 1) \cdot \prod_{o=b}^{p-1} m_{x_o}, & i = 1 \\ z_j^{i-1} + (x_{pa,b} - 1) \cdot m_{z_j} + \sum_{p=b+1}^e (x_{pa,p} - 1) \cdot m_{z_j} \prod_{o=b}^{p-1} m_{x_o}, & i > 1 \end{cases} \quad (43)$$

703 (4) Then, the value of the x_{temp} -th row and z^i_j -th column of CPT will be incremented by $p_{a,k}$,
704 i.e., Eq. (44);

$$705 \quad \text{CPT}(x_{temp}, z^i_j) = \text{CPT}(x_{temp}, z^i_j) + p_{a,k} \quad (44)$$

706 (5) For the CPT of the first time slice, if $k < N$, let $k = k + 1$, and repeat step (2). For the CPT of
707 other time slices, if $i < T$, let $i = i + 1$, and repeat step (2); and
708 (6) Once step (5) stops, the final CPT should be normalized.

709 More details on the above computational algorithms refer to [2].

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Fig. 1 Modular reliability assessment framework for corroding RC structures

Fig. 2 Geometry schematic of a simply-supported RC beam

Fig. 3 Schematics of constitutive models for different materials: (a) concrete; (b) reinforcement; and (c) bond-slip

Fig. 4 MBN for reliability assessment of RC beams

Fig. 5 SBN of FEM for corroded RC beams

Fig. 6 DBNs for other models: (a) chloride-induced durability assessment; (b) analytical capacities of corroded RC beam; and (c) time-dependent reliability analysis

Fig. 7 Schematics of environmental model: (a) temperature; (b) humidity; and (c) chloride deposition

Fig. 8 Probability distribution of ULS occurrence caused by non-uniform corrosion over 50 years: (a) analytical mechanical model; and (b) FEM

Fig. 9 PMFs of critical nodes in MBN: (a) P_{Mu} at 3 years; (b) P_{Mu} at 21 years; (c) P_{Mu} at 39 years; (d) P_{Vu} at 3 years; (e) P_{Vu} at 21 years; (f) P_{Vu} at 39 years; (g) α_{s1} at 3 years; (h) α_{s2} at 21 years; (i) α_{s3} at 39 years;

Fig. 10 Mean and STD of P_{Mu} and P_{Vu} subject to different inspection results: (a) Mean of P_{Mu} ; (b) Mean of P_{Vu} ; (c) STD of P_{Mu} ; and (d) STD of P_{Vu}

Fig. 11 Time-dependent failure probability $p_{f,s1}$ of the beam under SLS1 and different inspection results

Fig. 12 Time-dependent failure probability $p_{f,s2}$ of the beam under SLS2 and different inspection results

Fig. 13 Time-dependent failure probability $p_{f,u}$ of the beam considering on ULS and different inspection results

Fig. 14 Failure modes of the corroding RC beam subjected to different inspection results and time slices: (a) 3 years; (b) 27 years; and (c) 48 years

Fig. 15 Time-dependent probability of two failure modes subjected to different scenarios: (a) flexural failure probability & exposure conditions; (b) shear failure probability & exposure conditions; (c) flexural failure probability & environmental models & chloride transport modes; and (d) shear failure probability & environmental models & chloride transport modes